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A STUDY ON ATTITUDE OF TEACHERS ABOUT TECHNO PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND THEIR PERFORMANCE WITH REFERENCE TO GENDER

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ABSTRACT

It aimed to know the attitude of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with reference to gender. The method utilized for the study was a survey, sample of 41 teachers of Belthangady Taluk were selected using a simple random sampling technique. It was carried out in 2021 on different school teachers of Belthangady Taluk with reference to gender. In such a pandemic situation Techno-pedagogical skills, is the need of the hour. This study will not only help teacher, teacher trainees but many other professionals to have an insight about the effective usage of techno-pedagogical skills in daily instruction and main thrust areas to be focussed upon for effective utilization of techno pedagogical skills in different aspects of life.

Keywords: Attitude, Techno-pedagogical skills.

Introduction:

The educational set-up has undergone a paradigm shift in teaching techniques due Covid-19 with the introduction of technologies in the school. Now a day's teaching is very hard to imagine without the help of technology. To inculcate such things in the classroom deeds, teachers have to become techno-pedagogue. Visualize if teachers teaching theories, by giving up the mechanical approach and making it interesting by simulating problems and finding solutions to such imaginary issues. Teachers with appropriate techno-pedagogical skills can make teaching a enjoyable without feeling much stress. Transformation from teachers to techno-pedagogue would not only increase the capability of the teachers but would also widen the knowledge base of students and make them competitive in the international arena. It will be interesting to know; how present teacher attitude to evolve as a techno-pedagogy skills in classroom.

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Koehler and Mishra (2005) found in their study that better teaching was not simply adding technology rather the introduction of technology causes the representation of new concepts and needs developing sensitivity to the dynamic, transactional relationship among technology, pedagogy, content and knowledge. ICT can be imaginatively drawn upon for professional development and academic support of the pre-service and in-service teachers stated by The National Curriculum Framework (2009).

Objectives:

1. To study attitude of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with reference to gender.
2. To study attitude of teachers towards Techno-Pedagogical skills with reference to gender.
3. To study attitude of teacher's performance in Techno-Pedagogical skills with reference to gender.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- H₁: There is significant difference between attitude of teachers towards about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender.
- H₂: There is significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher's towards Techno-Pedagogical skills.
- H₃: There is significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher's performance in Techno-Pedagogical skill.

Methodology:

In this study the investigator followed survey studies describes and investigator what exists at present in this study investigator wanted to know the attitude of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with reference to gender.

Population:

All the teacher of were taken as population and those teachers were related to Belthangady Taluk

Sample:

There are so many schools in Belthangady taluk researcher selected only few schools for this purpose researcher selected only 41 teachers including male and female this sample was selected by simple random sampling technique.

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Data collecting Tools:

Researcher oneself constructed and used the tool on attitude of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender using Google form by sending Google Link <https://forms.gle/7wVDcQKtEzpGFgLR9>. It was a likert type scale. The items were constructed up of 4 point scale options were Strongly Agree=4, Agree=3, Disagree=2, Strongly disagree=1. Descriptive Statistics were used to calculate mean, standard deviation and inferential statistics (t-test) used to analyse the data.

Findings and Discussion

41 respondents in this study, 10 (24.4%) of them were males while 31 (75.6%) of them were females.

In order to answer the research question this was on the attitude of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with reference to gender.

Table 1.0: View of teachers about Techno-Pedagogical skills

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percent	Decision
Including technology in Teaching, whether it improves learning outcomes form your learners.	Strongly Agree	20	48.8%	Agree
	Agree	21	51.2%	
	Total	41	100.0	
With your techno-teaching skills can you easily sustain the attention of your students in class	Strongly Agree	13	31.7%	Agree
	Agree	27	65.9%	
	Strongly disagree	1	2.4%	
	Total	41	100.0	
Techno-Teaching skills help to improve your students' participation in learning activities.	Strongly Agree	17	41.5%	Agree
	Agree	23	56.1%	
	Disagree	1	2.4%	
	Total	41	100.0	
Techno-Teaching skills improve your assessment quality.	Strongly Agree	8	19.5%	Agree
	Agree	29	70.7%	
	Disagree	4	9.8%	
	Total	41	100.0	
Whether Techno-	Strongly Agree	19	46.3%	Agree

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teaching skills helps to increase your career development	Agree	22	53.7%	
	Total	41	100.0	
Improvement in your techno-teaching skills, will improve your performance as a teacher.	Strongly Agree	18	43.9%	Agree
	Agree	21	51.2%	
	Disagree	2	4.9%	
	Total	41	100.0	

Table 1 showed the results obtained from the responses of the 41 sampled teachers.

For the first statement in the Table I exposed that an vast majority 21(51.2%) agreed, 20(48.8%) strongly agreed while no one disagreed to the statement that Including technology in Teaching, whether it improves learning outcomes form your learners and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

For the second statement in the Table I exposed that an vast majority 27(65.9%) agreed, 13(31.7%) strongly agreed while negligible 1(2.4%) disagreed to the statement that , With your techno-teaching skills can you easily sustain the attention of your students in class and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

For the Third statement in the Table I exposed that a vast majority 23(56.1%) agreed, 17(41.5%) strongly agreed while minor 1(2.4%) disagreed to the statement that ,Techno-Teaching skills help to improve your students’ participation in learning activities and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

For the forth statement in the Table I exposed that a vast majority 29(70.7%) agreed, 8(19.5%) strongly agreed while minor 4(9.8%) disagreed to the statement that, Techno-Teaching skills improve your assessment quality and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

For the fifth statement in the Table I exposed that a vast majority 22(53.7%) agreed, 19(46.3%) strongly agreed while no one disagreed to the statement that, Whether Techno-teaching skills helps to increase your career development and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

For the Sixth statement in the Table I exposed that a vast majority 21(51.2%) agreed, 18(43.9%) strongly agreed while minor 2(4.9%) disagreed to the statement that , Improvement in your techno-teaching skills, will improve your performance as a teacher and this led to the overall decision agree for the item.

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Table 2.0: View of teachers about their performance on Techno-Pedagogical skill

Variable	Description	Frequency	Percent	Decision
Your skills in using technology for teaching and learning is	Excellent	12	29.3%	Very Good
	Very good	15	36.6%	
	Good	14	34.1%	
	Total	41	100.0	
Use of techno-teaching improves your performance in teaching.	Strongly Agree	16	39%	Agree
	Agree	23	56.1%	
	Disagree	2	4.9%	
	Total	41	100.0	

Table II revealed that out of the 41 teachers sampled, the majority 15(36.6%) had Very good skills, 12(29.3%) are Excellent 14(34.4%) are good in the use of techno-Teaching tools. This led to the overall rate of the pedagogic skills of teachers is very good.

Table II further revealed that a total majority of 23(56.1%) of the respondents agreed while 2(4.9%) disagreed to the statement that Use of techno-teaching improves your performance in teaching and this led to the decision agree for that statement.

Data Analysis:

Analysis of objective One: To study attitude of teachers towards Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender.

H₀1: There is no significant difference between attitude of teachers towards about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender.

The test was employed to test hypothesis and level of significance fix at 0.05. The result of the test is given in the Table 3.0.

Table 3.0: t Test Details on attitude of teachers towards Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	Result
Male	10	27.7	1.734	1.977	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	31	25.96	2.558		

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From the Table 3.0 it is observed that the obtained t value 1.997 is less than the critical value 2.021. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 levels. It means there is no significant difference between attitude of teachers towards about Techno-Pedagogical skills and their performance with references to gender.

Analysis of objective Two: To study attitude of teachers towards Techno-Pedagogical skills with reference to gender.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher’s towards Techno-Pedagogical skills.

Table 4.0: t Test Details on attitude of teachers towards Techno-Pedagogical skills with references to gender.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t value	Result
Male	10	21.2	1.4	2.17	Significance at 0.05 level
Female	31	19.77	1.928		

From the Table 4.0 it is observed that the obtained t value 2.17 is greater than the critical value 2.021. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 levels and research hypothesis is retained. It means there is a significant difference between male and female teacher’s attitude towards Techno-Pedagogical skills.

Analysis of objective Three: To study attitude of teacher’s performance in Techno-Pedagogical skills with reference to gender.

H₀3: There is no significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher’s performance in Techno-Pedagogical skill.

Table 5.0: t Test Details on attitude of teacher’s performance in Techno-Pedagogical skills with reference to gender.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t value	Result
Male	10	6.5	1.204	0.734	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	31	6.193	1.119		

From the Table 5.0 it is observed that the obtained t value 0.734 is less than the critical value

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2.021.Hence the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 levels. It means there is no significant difference between attitude of attitude of male and female teacher’s performance in Techno-Pedagogical skill.

Findings of the study

- There is no significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher’s towards Techno-Pedagogical skills.
- There is significant difference between male and female teacher’s attitude towards Techno-Pedagogical skills.
- There is no significant difference between attitude of male and female teacher’s performance in Techno-Pedagogical skill.

Educational Implications:

- This study will help to policy maker and Teacher Educators to take care of this area and more emphasis should be given to development of techno-pedagogical skills and competencies teachers.
- Various workshop, seminar and skill development programmes will surely help to deal with professional growth of teacher

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